

چهارمین کنگره آموزشی خود مراقبتی و آموزش بیمار

خلاصه مقالات

چهارمین کنگره آموزشی خود مراقبتی و آموزش بیمار و اولین جشنواره آموزش بیمار

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The views of patients with Spinal cord injury on the educational needs of family and society

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Objective:

Spinal cord injury (SCI) causes many complications, which can be prevented or minimized through patient education (PE). One of the most important step in patient education is need assessment. The aim of this survey was the views of patients with SCI on the educational needs of family and society.

Methodology:

This research is based on a survey containing open- and closed-ended questions and a number of dichotomous questions. The questionnaire was emailed to the participants with spinal cord injuries who had been informed about the survey. All the variables have been coded by Descriptive Coding and Values Coding approaches.

Results:

Sixty one participants completed the questionnaire. The educational needs of family were: training on all fundamental and basic aspects related to their circumstance, psychological and communicative trainings. About the educational needs of society they believed that the society has not received the adequate cultural and social trainings, the lack or perhaps the scarce of social and behavioral skills are the greatest concerns of other patients who suffer from the SCI. They happen to believe the members of the society require receiving appropriate instruction to develop the common sense of understanding and acceptance the disabled members of the society.

Conclusion:

Understanding the educational needs of family and society lead to effective program of patient education.

Keywords: SCI, educational needs, family, society